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Effect of Electronic Health Care Kiosks Project on Students' Academic Achievement in Biomedical Engineering in Rivers State College of Health Science Management and Technology

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Abstract

The study determined the effect of electronic health care kiosks project on students' academic achievement in biomedical engineering in Rivers State College of Health Science Management and Technology. Three research questions guided the study while three null hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted quasi-experimental research design and was carried out in Rivers State. The population for the study comprised 30 national diploma (ND) II Biomedical students. There was no sampling because of manageable size of the population. The instrument for data collection was titled. Electronic Healthcare Kiosks Project achievement test (EHKP). The reliability co-efficient of the instrument was determined using Kuder Richardson formula 20 (KR-20). Data was collected through the use of pre and post-test questions. The data for the three research questions were analysed using mean and standard deviation. The hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance using analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). The findings of the study revealed that Students taught electronic repairs and maintenance with the electronic healthcare kiosks project performed better than those taught using lecture method, and students taught biomedical equipment/devices and instruments with the electronic healthcare kiosks project performed better than those taught using lecture method. Hence, recommendations include that periodic trainings and workshops should be organized by the government for all lecturers/instructors in Rivers State College of Health Science Management and Technology to acquaint them with how to improvise equipment for proper training of the students. Constant power supply to mount improvised machines for constant practice should be put in place in Rivers State College of Health Science Management and Technology.

Keywords: biomedical engineering, electronic health care, electronic repairs, maintenance